

The University of Manchester,
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*Design Thinking and eco-efficient
innovative engineering*

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Abstract

Business research interest in innovation is increasing. Design Thinking has been presented as a process that promotes innovation and has, therefore, captured the interest of the business community. A literature review showed that when it comes to define key concepts or present successful implementations of Design Thinking, ambiguous definitions and little detail are given. Using a cybernetic perspective Design Thinking was reframed and a definition of Design Thinking that makes “organic” sense is justified. To understand if Design Thinking applies to the development of innovative engineering products for single clients, two eco-efficient projects are studied. Results from this study show that the definition given to Design Thinking applies not only for products/ services for markets, but also for products/ services for single clients. Suggestions for engineering companies that wish to frame the development of eco-efficient innovative projects according to the design thinking process are presented.

Keywords: Design thinking, innovation, eco-efficiency, cybernetics.

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Introduction

In the last decade Design Thinking has received much attention from the business community. Being a recent concept, Design Thinking is under close scrutiny, and it seems to be one of those “things” that lead to an either love or hate relationship. As Figure 1 shows, those that champion the concept — notably, Roger Martin from Rotman School of Management, who promotes and develops the concept since 2004 (e.g., Martin 2004, Dunne and Martin 2006, Martin 2010, Leavy 2011, Martin and Euchner 2012) — should be glad to know that 2012 has seen a significant increase in publications including “Design Thinking” on their titles¹.

Figure 1: Number of publications that include “Design Thinking” on their titles.

However, strong objections have been raised against the concept. There are two broad groups of objectors: design researchers, that often credit the concept as “marketing for design firms” (Merholz, 2009) and ask for the “death” of the “Design Thinking” designation (Dorst, 2011, p. 531); and, business researchers. Objections from this last group are, in the short run, more meaningful. Bruce

¹Data from the *Business Source Premier* business research database was used in Figure 1. Business Source Premier database includes “more than 2,200 journals” and covers “all disciplines of business, including marketing, management, MIS, POM, accounting, finance and economics” (<http://www.ebscohost.com/academic/business-source-premier>, accessed on March 2013).

Nussbaum, that in 2005 championed the concept and had set himself to show the tools, methods, and metrics to “help make” Design Thinking (Nussbaum, 2005), recently declared: “Design Thinking is a failed experiment”; and, “The decade of Design Thinking is ending” (Nussbaum, 2011). According to Bruce Nussbaum, his experience with Design Thinking became disturbing:

“... when you say the word ‘design’ to people across a table, they tend to smile politely and think ‘fashion.’ Say ‘design thinking,’ and they stop smiling and tend to lean away from you.”
(Nussbaum, 2011)

Bruce Nussbaum recognizes a very low success rate of Design Thinking processes and attributes this to CEO and managers unwillingness to accept the mess² that comes along with the process of real innovation.

Both critics and champions of the Design Thinking concept agree that there is a general confusion about the nature and the merit of the “undefinable term” Design Thinking (Dorst, 2011; Walters, 2011; Whitney, 2013). According to Walters (2011) there is no “consensus on a definition of design thinking, let alone agreement as to who’s responsible for it, who actually executes it (...).”

Perhaps due to the hype that it generated in the business community, Design Thinking is regarded by many as a buzz concept doomed to be replaced by “the next thing”. Its relative novelty and multifaceted nature justifies, perhaps, the lack of a definitive meaning to the concept, and a clear set of rules on how to use it. The present document hopes to contribute to a better understanding of the meaning of Design Thinking, and find out if the design thinking process can help engineering companies develop successful eco-efficient innovative projects.

This document is divided in two parts. Part I is based on literature review and explores the topic of Design Thinking for the development of innovative products/ services for the market. In chapter 1, while answering the question “why Design Thinking?”, a narrative for the sequence of events that led to the “birth” of Design Thinking as a business concept is proposed. Chapter 2 presents the design thinking process, its tools and discusses its limitations. Chapter 3 attempts to explain the meaning of frequently used concepts which are left undefined in Design Thinking literature, such as: meaning-based needs, unarticulated needs, or the failing fast concept. To help give meanings to these concepts a cybernetic perspective is considered.

Part II uses Design Thinking to frame the development of innovative products/ services for a single client. Chapter 4 starts by introducing innovative eco-efficient engineering projects implemented in two different clients. Details on the clients, on the innovative product/ service provider and the timelines of events that led to innovation are presented. The timelines of events are then

²See Ackoff (1981).

used to test the fit of a design thinking process consisting of the following stages: (i) immersion into the market/ client's culture; (ii) framing/ reframing; (iii) rapid prototyping. If there is a fit, the design thinking process could be used to promote eco-efficient innovative engineering projects.

Finally, on the concluding chapter, characteristics of Design Thinking that are considered by some as problems are discussed. A definition of Design Thinking that applies when developing products/ services for markets or for single clients is given. The implementation of the design thinking process by engineering companies that develop eco-efficient innovative projects is discussed.

Part I
Design Thinking with a
focus on markets:
Literature review

Chapter 1

Why Design Thinking?

1.1 Innovation as a necessity

Traditionally, it is assumed that the distribution curve differentiating the customer base is bell-shaped, enabling the identification of a company's market with the majority that fits one big category alone — see Figure 1.1a. To determine the products desired properties the consumer base preferences are used, while the preferences of smaller groups of consumers are ignored. Struggle for a share in such a market leads to intense competition. However, smaller groups of consumers “are taking over, and the bell-shaped curve is flattening out, as presented in Figure 1.1b” (Gharajedaghi, 2011, p. 189). Gharajedaghi argues that “targeting and understanding behaviours of the smaller groups that are emerging rapidly provides the best, and sometimes only, window of opportunity for a new player to successfully enter the game and skillfully avoid the intense competition at the early stages of the entry to a new [global] market.”

Figure 1.1: Distribution of customer base: a) Traditional bell-shaped; b) Flattening bell-shaped (Gharajedaghi, 2011, p. 189).

Realizing this “flattening out” of the customer base curve had a tremendous influence in business strategies. Non-price factors were recognized as determinant for competitiveness and to face the increasingly segmented global markets the mass customisation concept was perfected and implemented. According to Whyte et al. (2005, p. 7) “emphasis moved from supply struggling to catch

up with demand to a position where basic needs had been met, there was full employment and customers were becoming more discerning”.

Table 1.1 (Whyte et al., 2005) presents the shifting patterns of order-winning and order-qualifying factors, showing that in the early-2000s the customers order-winning critical success factors included customization.

Table 1.1: Shifting patterns of order-winning and order-qualifying factors (Whyte et al., 2005, p. 8).

Time period	Order-qualifying critical success factors	Order-winning critical success factors
Pre 1970	Availability	Price
1970s	Availability, price	Quality
1980s	Availability, price, quality	Differentiation
1990s	Availability, price, quality, differentiation	Time to market with new products
2000	Availability, price, quality, differentiation, time to market with new products	Price, customisation

To face these new challenges, companies needed to understand the smaller groups of customers, and to be able to deliver different products to a large number of smaller groups. Innovation was recognized as an important competitive force and interest in design grew. It was recognized that design was often less capital intensive and had a shorter pay-back period than for example technological research, while keeping the potential to drive competitiveness (EC, 2009, p. 2).

1.2 Design: A source of innovations

By late-1990s early-2000s, in a period where companies innovation resources were scarce but, at the same time, customers no longer wanted the same products — recall Table 1.1 — the work designers and design consulting companies were doing developing and promoting innovative products grabbed the business community attention (e.g., Boland Jr., 2004; Kelley et al., 2001). Design became recognised as a catalyser for creativity, for product innovation, for organisational change (Cameron, 2003; Martin, 2004).

Many examples testified the ability design had to discover new purposes to existing technologies and to discover how to apply new technologies to existing customer needs. *Designed communication strategies* had also shown the ability design had to shape the consumers perception of companies³.

³An emblematic example of the extraordinary power of design is the work of designers Charles and Ray Eames and their cooperation with several large companies between the 1960

Buchanan’s third broad area of design (Buchanan, 1992) — design of activities and organized services, which includes “the traditional management concerns for logistics, combining physical resources, instrumentalities, and human beings in efficient sequences and schedules to reach specific objectives” — fully justified the use of Design’s⁴ methods and working approaches in business management to promote creativity and product innovation. The fundamental questions were: What are these methods and approaches? How can they be used in business context?

Design is done in so many different professions (e.g., graphic designers, industrial designers, engineers, designers-cum-managers, architects, urban planners) that certainly, regardless of the professional area, the way designers think, the way they ideate, must possess unifying characteristics.

Theory of Design had been a topic of intense academic research and debate since the late-1960s and, by early-2000s, was recognised as a mature and independent research subject with specific methods and tools (Cross, 2006; Jones, 1992; Santos, 2010; Simon, 1988). A link between design-specific methods and tools and innovation became inevitable. As Roger Martin (2004) defended, translating these methods and tools into the business context provided the means for transforming traditional businesses into innovative “Design Shops”.

1.2.1 Discovering solutions

Central to the study of innovation is the process of having an idea, an intuition, of “discovering” a problem and discovering its solution.

The study of ideation belongs to the field of psychology and neuroscience, and it is important to distinguish between the study of having an idea and the logical evaluation of the methods and results of having had the idea. In fact, according to Popper (1996), there is no logical method to generate ideas or logically trace back the process of ideating. Damasio (2005), who quotes Henri Poincaré on the subject of how to arrive at a mathematical law, argues that ideas come from choosing facts *worth being studied*, and, by a process of *analogy to other facts*, solutions may be derived. Non-productive combination of facts don’t even cross the innovators mind; they don’t surface to conscience unless they are useful; if they surface and are rejected it is because they had something of a useful combination of facts. Damasio considers intuition as a process where not all combinatorial possibilities are studied, enabling a quicker process of arriving to a solution.

and 1970; especially the work done with IBM (Eames and Eames, 1968, 1990, 2012).

⁴Design *with a capital D*, articulated by Cross as “the collected experience of the material culture, and the collected body of experience, skill and understanding embodied in the arts of planning, inventing, making and doing.” (in Cross, 1982; see also Cross, 2006).

This is perhaps the reason why seniority is useful — Through experience the possible solutions can be reduced from a large to a small set⁵. Results presented by Casakin’s study on expert versus novice performance show that experts arrive to the solution making use of their repository of facts (experience), selecting boundaries that help focus on a small set of possible solutions; and even considering constraints that were not originally specified in the problem definition, as a way to get to a solution (Casakin, 2003). When compared with an experienced designer the novice is in disadvantage due to his inability to select boundaries and reject useless solutions⁶.

Figure 1.2, from Gharajedaghi (2011), illustrates the designer’s process of deriving a solution, by imposing successive boundaries to the specification of the *desired future next generation design* and taking into consideration “what is relevant and supportive to our *shared vision of a desirable future*” (Gharajedaghi, 2011, p. 150): the “existing mess” in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: “Designerly” way of deriving a solution using successive framing and re-framing (Gharajedaghi, 2011, p. 148).

Hugh Dubberly’s Figure 1.3 clarifies the meaning of *shared vision* (represented by the large ellipse uniting designer and its interlocutor), contrasting it with designer-specific processes (smaller ellipses).

The successive approximations of Figure 1.2 — the successive framing and reframing of the problem, according to Dorst (2011) or Beckman and Barry (2007) — is necessary when conflicting statements in the desired future design exist. When this happens design researchers speak of “ill-defined” problems (Cross, 1982), “wicked” problems (Buchanan, 1992) or say that the problem

⁵Therefore the importance of the hands-on approach in design (e.g., extensive use of mock-up building, immersion in the user/consumer cultural setting).

⁶However, this characteristic of the novice is the same that makes him potentially more creative; for his mindset is not yet formatted by past experience, leaving him with a much wider set of possible solutions.

Figure 1.3: Shared vision and designer-specific processes juxtaposed (http://www.dubberly.com/models/feedback_loops1.html, accessed on April 2013).

presents “a real paradox” (Dorst, 2011). According to Dorst (2011, p. 527), designers start working towards a solution only after “the nature of the core paradox has been established to [the designers] satisfaction. (...) It was found that the best expert designers do not address the core paradox head-on, but tend to focus on issues around it. They search (...) new frames with which to tackle the central paradox (...)”.

Through experience, successive framing and reframing; through sheer intensity of thought, designers acquire an understanding of materials, products or systems⁷ that allows them to understand these materials, products or systems *true value*, giving them a meaningful *gestalt*. This ability to discover solutions to “ill-posed” problems is a significant advantage if it is equipped with instruments capable of probing social systems — probing markets —; instruments used for providing data relevant for framing and solving the complex problems that business managers face.

1.3 Market probing methods

1.3.1 Ethnographic market research

The “designerly way of knowing” applied to the business context implied an in-depth knowledge of the market, of users and customers needs. However, decades of training had taught executives to focus not on the value their products provided for their customers but on proxies for it. As discussed previously — recall Table 1.1 —, by late-1990s early-2000s markets behaviour were changing

⁷Social scientists acquire an understanding of specific cultural settings; designers-cum-business-managers acquire an understanding of specific business settings.

and it was recognized that traditional market research methods were insufficient to understand the changes that were taking place:

“They [customers] no longer wanted undifferentiated goods (...) [t]hey no longer wanted poor quality goods, with low product lives and high recall rates. But, perhaps most importantly, they no longer wanted the same goods — consumers increasingly began to see themselves as individuals or as members of distinct, and increasingly, of small consuming groups.” (Whyte et al., 2005)

Understanding what consumers valued in a highly segmented market asked for alternative market research tools; even traditional qualitative tools such as focus groups no longer delivered the information needed. There was this increased need for user-centred data, allowing for user-centred innovation⁸. Liedtka articulates this need (and its connection with Design Thinking) quite eloquently:

“There is a big difference between knowing your customer well enough to sell better and knowing them sufficiently well to identify their unarticulated needs. Unarticulated needs — not requests from purchasing — are the most secure source of new ideas that have true competitive advantage (and hence higher margins). (...) So, analytical methods are not enough, you need to immerse yourself in the customers deep needs. Design Thinking methodologies are based not on knowing the customer from sales reports, but from immersing into the customer world and understanding their deepest needs.” (Liedtka, 2011, p. 16)

The value of getting into a respondent’s *natural life world* became increasingly apparent, ethnographic methods started being used alongside traditional methods; it was found that “[t]horough understanding of customer and user needs is generated through observational or ethnographic research that seeks to understand not only the fundamental use and usability needs of the customer or user, but also the *meaning-based needs*.” (Beckman and Barry, 2007, italics added) Beckman and Barry’s article describes how ethnographic market research methods can be used to “bring the process of innovation alive” and describes ethnographic techniques — “[t]he observer seeks to understand why users act as they do, and how users make sense of what they do for themselves and for others. The observer elicits and listens to stories, particularly stories that involve contradictions or workarounds, spoken and unspoken norms (that if not met, may jeopardize the success of the innovation) (...)”

⁸User-centred innovation should not be mistaken with user-led or user-driven innovation (as addressed in Kitson, 2011), or even with crowdsourcing techniques.

1.3.2 Rapid prototyping

If ethnographic market research is a method “designerly” businesses have for observing the market and help framing/ reframing complex business problems; rapid prototyping is the method that is used to test solutions.

Prototyping is part of designers *modus operandi*. Architects, engineers, industrial designers have always relied on scale models and mock-ups to test their designs and, more recently, software engineers test their designs by creating graphic user interfaces that show the end user what the software will look like without building the whole underlying functionality software.

Prototypes are made to understand if the design will solve the problem that is being addressed, or if it will fail. Experimenting, failing, is an integral part the design process; *rapid* prototyping aims at *failing fast*. Fogg describes the meaning of *failing fast*:

“This [failing fast] means investing only a few hours in a trial that might not work. In contrast, projects that require months or years should not fail; that’s a waste of time and money. Large projects will succeed when built on a foundation of *many small, measurable successes*.” (Fogg, 2009, italics added)

An example of Design Thinking that illustrates the use of rapid prototyping in the business context is described by (Liedtka, 2011). After several *small* failed experiments, finally a manager from the pharmaceutical sector succeeds in finding a new “win” product; the product’s concept is analysed to understand the user/ customer behaviour that justifies the “win”. It is this product’s concept that is used when expanding to other new products.

But Liedtka also mentions the importance of rapid prototyping the *supply chain*; the importance of finding the right retailers and the right “product-and-package” combination. Liedtka describes small-scale experiments with selected retailers and concludes that these were decisive in finding the necessary (supply chain) allies.

From Liedtka’s example it is possible to conclude that rapid prototyping advocates an initial “think small” approach to check for failure, and expanding on successful solutions only after the underlying principles of success and failure are sufficiently tested. And it should be noted, as Fogg (2009) describes, that the tests need not be scientific experiments “... but quick trials that allow the design team to prototype the experience and see how people [users/ customers/ the market] react[s].”

1.4 Conclusion

Why Design Thinking? A possible answer to the question is: By late-1990s early-2000 markets became increasingly segmented; consumers no longer wanted undifferentiated goods and the ability to innovate was recognised as an important competitive force. Design consultancies were recognized by the business community as a way to promote innovation; Theory of Design had matured and “designerly” methods and tools that fostered innovation were readily available; in-depth market probing methods and tools were also available. The concept of Design Thinking was “born” and provided, in a business-oriented/ innovation-driven package, a convenient combination of all the above methods and tools.

Chapter 2

Design Thinking process and tools

In this chapter the design thinking process proposed by Beckman and Barry (2007) is described.

Beckman and Barry merged models from the fields of design and education; they recognised the complementary nature of Kolb’s experiential learning model, which includes experiencing, reflecting, thinking and acting stages, and Owen’s design process model, which considers both analytic (theoretical) and synthetic (practical) elements.

According to Beckman and Barry the design thinking process has the following four stages:

- Observation;
- Frameworks;
- Imperatives;
- Solutions.

The next sections present details on these stages.

2.1 Observation

Beckman and Barry believe observation of the customer needs should rely on ethnographic research. According to these researchers ethnographic research enables the understanding of “not only the *fundamental* use and usability needs of the customer or user, but also the meaning-based needs.”

Beckman and Barry draw upon Mariampolski’s *Ethnographic for Marketeers: A Guide to Consumer Immersion* to support the importance for the consumer

satisfaction of time, place, conditions and circumstances within which aspirations are conceived, decisions are made and product usage takes place.

Beckman and Barry describe tools used to gather relevant information when doing ethnographic research:

- Participant observation, which includes mystery shopper, participant-as-observer;
- Non-participant observation, which may be done directly or indirectly (e.g., using video cameras);
- Formal ethnographic interviews;
- Intercepts; a kind of “hanging out” with users, having less formal conversations;
- Informal diaries, to uncover differences between what a user says he or she “usually does” versus what he or she “actually does”;
- Virtual ethnography or netnography, which are ways of adapting ethnographic research to study internet behaviour.

2.2 Frameworks

The second stage of Beckman and Barry’s design thinking process is frameworks. It is attempting to make sense of the data that was collected in the Observation stage, in order to focus on what is most important to the customer or user.

Frameworks include framing and reframing. To explain the meaning of framing/ reframing Beckman and Barry give an example related to the development of home furnishing. They start by framing the problem along two vectors of customer behaviour: neat versus messy and organised versus disorganised. According to this framing, for western culture, neat organised is good; messy disorganised is bad. Beckman and Barry support that this framing justifies the focus on furniture design for neat organised persons, but leaves plenty of space for reframing into neat disorganised and messy organised furniture design. The researchers ask: “might there be opportunity to help neat, but disorganised people with different [furniture design] solutions?” Beckman and Barry conclude that this question was possible due to the (two-dimensional) framing considered (neat-messy; organised-disorganised).

Reframing means adopting a different approach and perspective; Beckman and Barry consider that “the ultimate purpose of the framing step is to reframe to come up with a new story to tell about how the user might solve his or her

problems to come up with a new way of seeing the problem which in turn allows the team to come up with new solutions.”

Beckman and Barry propose the use of the AEIOU framework (classifying data gathered under activities, environments, interactions, objects and users), a tool to help find symbolic meanings to customers or users problems. Another tool that can be used is Beckman and Barry’s two-dimensional matrices based on the vectors selected to frame the problem.

2.3 Imperatives

The imperative stage is, according to Beckman and Barry, when a “description of the tangible benefits customers derive from using a product or service” is made. It is different from the set of features or capabilities the product or service must have to deliver those benefits.

According to Beckman and Barry “[imperatives] distils the insights from the framing activity to the essence of the goals [of the innovation team].”

An example is Hewlett-Packard’s imperative for the development of its first Deskjet design; the product development team was charged of developing a “laser-quality printer that prints on plain paper for under \$1000.”

Beckman and Barry specify no tools for this stage.

2.4 Solutions

At the end of the design thinking process Beckman and Barry say the design thinking process should return to the practical realm to generate solutions, choose the ones that best meet the imperatives and test them with potential customers or users.

According to Beckman and Barry the following tools are useful to derive solutions:

- Brainstorming to generate solutions;
- Concept selection;
- Concept testing.

2.5 Discussion

The previous sections associate Design Thinking with typical process stages and with specific tools. Design Thinking is presented as a formula for business success:

Business success = Innovation.
Innovation = Design Thinking.
Business success = Design Thinking.

Pangaro’s “designed” syllogism (Pangaro, 2010) is probably how some see (and sell) Design Thinking. However, the nature of the design thinking process makes it very much *context specific*. Walters (2011) writes on an article whose title reads “*Design Thinking*” *Isn’t a Miracle Cure...*: “there’s a reason that companies such as Procter & Gamble and General Electric were held up time and again as being the poster children of this new discipline [Design Thinking]. Smartly, they had defined it according to their own terms, executing initiatives that were appropriate to their own internal cultures. And that often left eager onlookers somewhat baffled as to how to replicate their success.”

The importance of context along with the fact that most of the case studies presented in business literature provide little detail on the experience gained from successful implementation of Design Thinking, does not contribute for managers and researchers belief in its *repeatability*. Prospective managers tend to believe that Design Thinking success stories are mostly based on intuition and accepting its risks, as the following quote from Walters (2011) on Steve Jobs’ ‘designerly’ approach suggests: “Note too Jobs’ approach to customer research: ‘It isn’t the consumers’ job to know what they want.’ Jobs is comfortable hanging out in the world of the unknown, and this confidence allows him to take risks and make intuitive bets (...). This approach of risk taking, of relying on intuition and experience rather than on the ‘facts’ provided by spreadsheets and data, is anathema to most analysis-influenced C-suite members.”

There is yet another characteristic of Design Thinking which probably justifies Nussbaum’s (2011) experience with managers that “stop smiling and ... lean away from you” at the sound of Design Thinking (see page 4) — Design thinking processes promote organisational change.

Walters (2011) description his perhaps helpful for understanding managers’ ambivalence towards Design Thinking:

“... it [Design Thinking] turns up insights galore, and there is real value and skill to be had from synthesizing the messy, chaotic, confusing and often contradictory intellect of experts gathered from different fields to tackle a particularly thorny problem. That’s all part of design thinking. And designing an organizational structure in which this kind of cross-fertilization of ideas can take place effectively is tremendously challenging, particularly within large organizations where systems and departments have become entrenched over the years.”

Fitting an existing organisation with the capability of framing and reframing problems in order to “discover” innovative solutions is no trivial process. But

this capability is essential for Design Thinking. Geoghegan and Pangaro (2009) provide important insights into what can happen when an organisation decides to implement a design thinking processes.

Chapter 3

Reframing Design Thinking

3.1 Cybernetics: Selected topics

3.1.1 Trivial and non-trivial machines

Figure 3.1: Foerster's machines: a) Trivial; b) Non-trivial (von Foerster, 2001b).

Figure 3.1 presents von Foerster's illustrations of trivial and non-trivial machines. In a trivial machine a function f models the dynamic behaviour of a system (physical or not), and relates its input x and corresponding output y .

According to von Foerster (2001b) the trivial machine is a synthetically determined, independent of past, analytical determinable, predictable system. Since it allows analytical representation, given an input (any input) it is possible to determine the output; this output is predictable, therefore the machine's behaviour is considered trivial, unchallenging.

On the other hand, von Foerster's non-trivial machine is also synthetically determined and analytically determinable, but, dependent on the past and unpredictable. The function F that relates the input x and the output y is defined

in terms of inner states z , whose values change (according to function Z) for each new forward (time) step from z to z' . Since the inner states z determine the analytical function F , a fixed input x can have different outputs y ; the output becomes therefore unpredictable, the machine’s behaviour is considered non-trivial, surprising⁹.

3.1.2 Black box, “muddy” box

Section 3.1.1 characterised von Foerster’s trivial and non-trivial machines as analytically determinable. For the non-trivial machine this implied the explicit definition of inner states z that determined the system’s behaviour at each new forward (time) step. Although not explicitly stated — and not shown in Figure 3.1a — the trivial machine has also inner states z . Contrary to what happens with the non-trivial machine, these remain constant regardless of the forward (time) step, justifying the trivial machine predictable behaviour.

The synthetic nature of von Foerster’s machines allows for the explicit knowledge of their “inner mechanics” (of the inner states z); however, in general, the inner mechanics of most natural systems isn’t readily accessible. All that can be known is the system’s outputs given some inputs. Systems with “hidden” mechanics — with *latent* inner states — are called *black boxes*.

The concept of black box is explored in many texts on cybernetics (Beer, 1994; Glanville, 2012). Glanville discusses the characteristics associated with the black box and compares it with von Foerster’s machines — see Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Similarities and differences between trivial and non-trivial machines, and a black box (Glanville, 2012, p. 167).

Trivial machine	Non-trivial machine	Black box
open	open	unopenable
observer uninvolved	observer uninvolved	observer involved
future predictable	future non-predictable	future non-predictable

Glanville introduces the “unopenable” attribute and attaches it to black boxes — All the black box observer can do is “construct an account for his observations of various input behaviours and their corresponding output behaviours.” (Glanville, 2012)

Glanville argues that although von Foerster’s machines are often conflated with the black box concept¹⁰, due to its “unopenability” the black box deserves a clear distinction from von Foerster’s open and analytically determinable machines. Glanville also concludes that a black box isn’t just a trivial machine that

⁹When a non-trivial machine is mistaken for a trivial one, this element of surprise is often interpreted as an error (Glanville, 2012).

¹⁰For example, Beer (1994) speaks of transparent *box* and opaque *box* when all and no inner states are observable, respectively.

happens to be unopenable; Glanville (2012) argues: “just because something has always happened, does not guarantee it will persist.”

A black box’s behaviour may have always been predictable, but since its behaviour is known just from limited records of inputs and outputs and its inner states are not *manifest* — they are *latent* —, there is no way of knowing if they have changed or will change, rendering useless all assumptions about the black box behaviour.

Most natural systems are neither open like von Foerster’s machines nor unopenable like black boxes. Beer (1994) calls these in-between systems “muddy” boxes.

Reframing

The wide scope of the black box concept, its association with transversal disciplines such as cybernetics and systems theory means that it is applicable to all fields of science. Socio-economic systems, the market, isn’t a fully open system, but enables the partial understanding of its output given some input. Using a cybernetic approach, from a managerial perspective the market is considered a muddy box relating users/ customers buys — the output — with product specifications — the input. The market inner states z are Beckman and Barry’s *meaning-based* needs, or Liedtka’s *unarticulated* needs (see section 1.3.1).

Figure 3.2: Market represented as a system with interrelated needs, which determine the function relating product specification and buy.

Understanding the market (the user/ customer) meaning-based needs represents an extraordinary competitive advantage, however,

Figure 3.2 makes clear that meaning-based needs and market output are different things. Needs are internal to the market; the output crosses the market's boundaries. Several needs may be related in complex ways with a single output.

Although not shown in Figure 3.2, some of the needs may be *latent*, unreachable to the observer's monitoring tools.

3.1.3 First-order cybernetic system

To introduce first-order cybernetic systems consider the example of a ship's course control. The ship's course needs to be maintained constant, however, due to disturbances — for example, due to changes in water current —, the ship's dynamics is such that for a fixed steering wheel position, when the current increases the course will deviate. If the ship's course is to be kept constant the steering wheel position has to change. But which wheel position should the helmsman choose? The helmsman objective is to maintain the ship in a certain course; but he is not acting upon the ship's course, he is adjusting the wheel position...

Figure 3.3 illustrates a course control system based on a feedback loop¹¹.

Figure 3.3: First-order cybernetic system exemplifying a ship's course control system.

¹¹The boxes in Figure 3.3 represent trivial machines relating inputs and outputs of different subsystems: the ship (dynamics), the controller, the actuator and the transducers.

In Figure 3.3 it is assumed that the helmsman has a compass. The periodic reading of the ship’s course is transduced by the helmsman’s eyes — the sensor — and transferred to the helmsman’s central nervous system (CNS) — the controller. The transduced course signal is compared with the transduced target course (e.g., a mark drawn in the compass) and, if different, the CNS commands an action — the result of the controller’s control law —, resulting in a movement of the helmsman’s hands — the actuator —, and a change in the steering wheel position.

This example explains what is known as the *feedback control loop*, and describes its basic components. Figure 3.4, from Pangaro (2011), illustrates how a ship’s course changes due to changes in water current and how the feedback control manages to cancel, through successive corrective actions, the error between the target and ship’s actual course.

First-order cybernetic systems are feedback control systems of the type just described.

Figure 3.4: Successive corrective actions resulting from the feedback control loop (Pangaro, 2011, p. 41).

There are alternatives to feedback control, for example, feedforward control; or a combination of feedback and feedforward control¹². Figure 3.5 compares simplified representations of feedback and feedforward control loops.

Contrary to feedback, that uses the output of the controlled system to synthesise a corrective action, feedforward uses measurable disturbance data. As highlighted in Figure 3.5, not all disturbances are measurable; in the ship’s example above, along with the water current strong side winds can also push the ship out of its course. A feedforward mechanism tuned to cancel errors due to water current conditions would fail to maintain the target course in varying wind conditions. Advantages and disadvantages of different types of control

¹²Heylighen and Joslyn add another type of perturbation control: *buffering*, “the *passive* absorption or damping of perturbations”. (Heylighen and Joslyn, 2001, p. 13, italics added)

Figure 3.5: Control concepts: a) Feedback; b) Feedforward (based on Eronini, 1999, p. 698).

systems are discussed in books of Control Theory (see, for example, Eronini, 1999).

Reframing

It is possible to adapt first-order cybernetics concepts to the study of business processes. Figure 3.6 from Karapetrovic and Willborn (1998) depicts a Service Quality System feedback control loop.

Figure 3.6: Service Quality feedback control loop (Karapetrovic and Willborn, 1998, p. 262).

Figure 3.7 presents a possible Business System feedback control loop with explicit controller, actuator and transducer — depicted as concept development units (e.g., design, local coordination), produc-

tion units (e.g., production, marketing, sales), market research unit, respectively — and considering the market as the controlled system.

Figure 3.7: Example of a Business System feedback control loop depicting the market as the controlled system.

3.1.4 Second-order cybernetic system

The feedback control loop used in first-order cybernetic machines is a cornerstone in Cybernetic Theory. When the disturbances cause only minor departures from the controlled system's equilibrium position the first-order cybernetic machine is capable of maintaining a specific target/ goal/ setpoint; however, when the controlled system behaviour deviates significantly from equilibrium the first-order machine's target must be revised. Second-order cybernetic deals with the study of control systems with moving targets.

Figure 3.8, by Dubberly and Pangaro, represents the nested feedback loop that characterizes second-order cybernetic machines.

The larger feedback loop uses the output of the controlled system — described as the “Environment”; which is controlled by the smaller first-order machine's feedback loop —, to synthesise the first-order machine's “Goal”. The loop hierarchy justifies the *Observing System* and *Observed System* designations for larger and smaller loops, respectively.

Higher order feedback loops used to set the goal of second-order loops are conceivable. Figure 3.9 presents an example by Pangaro of a second-order cybernetic machine with three nested feedback loops.

Figure 3.8: Second-order cybernetic system (Dubberly and Pangaro, 2007, p. 1308).

Figure 3.9: Example of three nested feedback loops (Pangaro, 2013).

Reframing

Using second-order cybernetics Geoghegan and Pangaro (2009) address the issue of designed organisational change and contribute to the understanding of CEO's ambivalence towards Design Thinking (recall the discussion of Design Thinking limitations on section 2.5).

Geoghegan and Pangaro use a second-order cybernetic machine — see Figure 3.10^a — to study the process by which a CEO sets business goals in second-order control loops.

Figure 3.10: Second-order cybernetic machine as presented by Geoghegan and Pangaro (2009, p. 157).

If a market — the environment — is subject to minor disturbances the first-order control loop is sufficient to cancel their influence on the controlled output and maintain the CEO's goal — maintain equilibrium. However, if the market's output is approaching unacceptable limits^b the CEO must intervene and set alternative goals for the first-order loop; repeatedly, if necessary, until a new equilibrium state in which to lock-in is reached. A visual interpretation of the process of reaching a new equilibrium is presented in Figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11: Behaviour trajectories after a disturbance is introduced in a system (Ashby, 1960, p. 93).

It is obvious from Figure 3.11 that the new equilibrium is reached in a different stateplane (with inner state $z_3 = S$) that differs from the initial one (with $z_3 = 0$). The curves in Figure 3.11 go from the lower to the higher plane after the disturbance in the inner state z_3 takes place, and in a business context analogy these lines can be interpreted as the trajectories of meaning-based needs after a disturbance is introduced and the convergence of these needs to a new attractor; to a new equilibrium state^c.

When a market is attracted to a new equilibrium position leaving the previous one, the existing first-order feedback control goals become obsolete. The second-order control loop — the CEO — needs to understand the nature of the change and change these goals.

According to Geoghegan and Pangaro when businesses are forced to try new equilibria states; when new behaviour are needed, the original business “language” is useless for expressing the error that is taking place in the second-order feedback loop. In these authors opinion:

“When new errors fall outside the local limitations of language, the social system is at risk. The corporation is doing the wrong things, its version of the truth is faulty, and the individuals inside the corporation ‘do not know that they do not know’ (von Foerster, 2001a).”
(Geoghegan and Pangaro, 2009)

Geoghegan and Pangaro support planning for change; planning for embedding second-order cybernetic loops in the organisational structure, enabling the variety needed to cope with — or to lead! — market change. Without the planning “... it is nearly impossible for an existing organisation to come to a new belief system (...) without destroying the existing system. The individuals — weather deep in the hierarchy or the excess at the top — are too vulnerable, and their need to be secure and know that they can make a living and survive (...) is too great to be comfortable in the face of the necessary change.” (Geoghegan and Pangaro, 2009, p. 165)

This “C-suite members” resistance to embrace change justifies the decline of once large corporations and the difficulty large corporations have in discovering their “second big idea” (Whitney, 2013).

The implementation of design thinking processes forces organisational changes; this probably justifies the success Design Thinking has had in newly formed organisations (e.g., spin-off and start-up companies) and the difficulties felt in translating this success into established organisations^d. Unless, of course, change is already part of the company and CEO’s ethos.

^aFigure 3.10 shows a simplified representation of a first-order feedback loop (Feedback 1, on the left) connecting the environment to a control system (described as “observed behaving entity”). A second-order feedback loop (Feedback 2, on the right) is represented by a gauge and a behaviour fields (BF n , $n=1,2,\dots$) control box. This second-order observer loop receives information from the environment and determines the goals (the BF n s) used by the first-order observed loop.

^bUsing the concepts introduced in section 3.1.2, if disturbances caused by a competitor’s product or by a change in the market’s socio-economic fabric significantly influences the meaning-based needs.

^cIBM’s mid-1990s business focus shift from the personal computer to global services integration is a good example of locking-in to a new equilibrium state and helps understand the “behaviour fields” designation used in Figure 3.10.

^dOn this subject Walters (2011) writes: “... something of a problem [with design thinking processes] emerged. For all the gushing success stories that we and others wrote, most were often focused on one small project executed at the periphery of a multinational organization. When we stopped and looked, it seemed like executives had issues rolling out design thinking more widely throughout the firm.

3.2 A first-order cybernetics approach

3.2.1 The state observer

Figure 3.5a of section 3.1.3 described a control system based on the feedback signal from a controlled system output. However, sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2 explained that the inner states z are responsible for the way the controller system relates input and output; in this sense, inner states determine the system’s output.

If the inner states determine a system’s output an alternative to output feedback control is (inner) state feedback control. To implement state feedback control it is necessary to monitor the inner states. This introduces some problems, since:

- The monitoring instruments may be accurate, but the measured system variables may be noisy;
- Perhaps the system isn’t known with sufficient detail to determine which inner states to monitor;
- Even if all the relevant inner states are identified, the lack of measuring instruments (e.g., yet to be developed) may make them unreachable.

output variability¹³.

A legitimate question is: “Is the model of the controlled system uniquely determined?” The answer is no. There are many possible models representing the controlled system behaviour and these models may include different representations of inner states. From Control Theory it is known that there is a representation of the controlled system inner states that best represents the manifest (the observable) inner states, and that this representation has the smallest dimension (the smaller number of inner states).

Reframing

Section 1.3 explained the importance ethnographic market research had in the design thinking process. Ethnographic market research provides the observing capabilities traditional market research lacks and enables user-centred product development. According to Beckman and Barry (2007) ethnographic market research provides the customers “meaning-based needs”; Liedtka (2011) expresses the same idea using the expression “unarticulated needs”. In the cybernetic jargon both Beckman’s and Liedtka’s expressions are equivalent to *discovering the market/ customer/ user inner states*.

Traditional market research can be associated with Figure 3.3 and 3.5a with the transducer that feeds back market output/ behaviour to the controller. Ethnographic market research, on the other hand, can be associated with Figure 3.12 and with the observer that determines estimates of the market/ users/ customers meaning-based needs.

It is from the knowledge of the market meaning-based needs that the designer defines the market related constraints he will use (together with production, budgetary and other constraints) in the framing-reframing of design problems (recall Figure 1.2).

Figure 3.13 illustrates the role ethnographic market research has in the design thinking process. Notice that it was drawn inside (immersed in) the market, providing information about the meaning-based needs to the designer. This information is, however, truncated. Only the observable/ manifest needs are accessible to ethnographic research, as discussed in the next section.

¹³This subject is discussed in 3.2.2.

Figure 3.13: Interactions between ethnographic market research, the market meaning-based needs and the designer's process of framing-reframing of a problem.

3.2.1.1 Innovations

In the previous section the working principle of the state observer wasn't discussed in detail. What is the meaning of the error that is fed back into the observer? How are the estimates of the controlled system inner states adjusted?

Figure 3.12 shows that the state observer receives the same control input as the controlled system, but is driven by an error feedback, in other words, by a signal that expresses how much the controlled system output differs from the estimated observer output. It can be said that the observer is driven by *innovations*.

Willems and Polderman describe the logic beneath the state observer working principle:

“... [it] functions not unlike what happens in daily life. Suppose that we meet a friend. How do we organize our thoughts in order to deduce his or her mood, or other latent properties, from the observed manifest ones? Based on past experience, we have an ‘internal model’ of our friend in mind, and an estimate of the ‘associated state’ of his/her mood. This tells us what reactions to expect. When we observe an action or hear a response, then this

may cause us to update the state of this internal model. If the observed reaction agrees with what we expected from our current estimate, then there is no need to change the estimate. The more the reaction differs from our expectations, the stronger is the need to update. The difference between what we actually observe and what we had expected to observe is what we call the innovations. Thus it is logical to assume that the updating algorithm for the estimate of the internal model is driven by the innovations. We may also interpret the innovations as the *surprise factor*.” (Willems and Polderman, 1997, p. 351)

Reframing

Translating the first-order cybernetic concept of innovations to the business context the following definition of innovation is possible: It is a measure of the deviation of the market/ user/ customer/ behaviour (its output) from what would be expected given the existing knowledge — the existing model — of the market/ user/ customer behaviour.

It follows from this definition that innovation is related to the market behaviour, to the controlled system, not to any input given to the market.

This justifies a distinction between being *creative* — being concept-driven —, and being *innovative* — being results-driven. A person or an organisation can be creative, producing many *potential* innovations, but if in the end the market doesn’t recognise usefulness in the creative concepts, the person or organisation aren’t innovative.

The meaning given here to creativity and innovativeness coincides with that of Govindarajan (2010) and Marshall (2013); the fact that it was derived “naturally” from the discussion of first-order cybernetics and state observer testifies for the advantage of using the “lens” of cybernetics to reframe business concepts.

Taking a step further in the discussion of the difference between creativity and innovation, it can be said that if creativity is a market input (exists upstream), innovation is its corresponding output (exists only downstream), as shown in Figure 3.14.

Figure 3.14: The market depicted as a creativity (band-pass) filter.

In this sense, the market is a creativity filter^{a,b}. Sections 3.2.2 and 3.2.3 explain the process by which the market filters creativity, which is related to the way the market’s meaning-based needs “resonate”, given the creative concept inputs; and also to the observer ability to learn about this market’s meaning-based needs resonance^c.

^aInnovation funnel is an expression frequently used to convey this same idea (Haour, 2004, p. 37); however, the analogy to a funnel is inadequate. From a cybernetic point of view (fluid mechanics tells us that), not only a funnel preserves all incoming creative concepts (mass flow rate is preserved), but it also increases the creative concepts “velocity” whilst decreasing the “pressure” due to these concepts...

^bA company’s innovation efficiency can be assessed from the filtering characteristic of the market. Beside the obvious index defined as the ratio between innovations revenue and creative concepts development spendings (a time-to-innovation index could be defined in a similar way), borrowing concepts from the field of machinery lubrication a *beta ratio* ($\beta_{n \cdot k \cdot \mathcal{L}}$) could be defined after classifying creative concepts according to their expected revenue and determining for each class the ratio between the number of creative concepts converted into actual innovations worth the expected $n \cdot k \cdot \mathcal{L}$ revenue and the number of creative concepts in the class. An innovation efficiency based on the β ratio could be determined using $1/\beta$.

^cSections 3.2.2 and 3.2.3 show that neither the ability to influence the market (controllability) nor the ability to observe the market (observability) can be taken for granted.

3.2.2 Observability

Section 3.2.1 implicitly assumed that all the system’s inner states were manifest and could be “reached” from the system’s output (and corresponding input). Section 3.1.2 had already discussed that most natural systems are neither open nor unopenable, therefore some inner states remain unreachable; are latent.

The concept of *observability* is used in Control Theory to assess the way a system’s inner states relate to its monitored output, and to determine if there are latent inner states that do not manifest themselves through the output. Observability is defined as the “property that makes it possible to determine *any initial state* (...) of an *unforced* system by using a *finite record* of the output (...)” (Tewari, 2002). In other words, observability is a property which enables us to determine what the system was at an initial instant, after measuring the system output data for a finite time interval beginning at the initial instant. If all system’s inner states influence/ shape the output then the system is observable, since it is possible to reconstruct the input and determine what the system was at the initial instant from observing the output. However, if there are system’s

inner states that do not influence/ shape the output, then the system will be unobservable¹⁴. Unobservable systems are those that have latent inner states; therefore, some inner states cannot be determined from records of the system's output.

Lets consider a system similar to that in Figure 3.1a, but whose function relating input and output can be decomposed into n different subspaces. If one or more of these subspaces are unobservable, this implies that there will be no connection between the subspaces and the system' output, as illustrated in Figure 3.15, which assumes $n = 4$. In Figure 3.15 the inner states associated with subspaces P and R are unobservable. There is no connection between these states and the output y .

Figure 3.15: Example of a system with observable (Q and S) and unobservable (P and R) subspaces.

3.2.2.1 Reasons for unobservability

Unobservability is related to:

- *The choice of monitored output:* Observability depends on the controlled system output y that is monitored. For a given system output, observability does not depend on the observer, it is a characteristic of the controlled system. However, in some cases it is the observer's prerogative to choose the controlled system output to monitor. In this case, latent inner states for an output selection may become manifest using a different selection of the monitored outputs.
- *The choice of the model of the controlled system:* Section 3.1.3 discussed the derivation of a model for the controlled system from knowledge of the system's inputs and outputs and it was then stated that models with

¹⁴Often a researcher senses that a system variable ought to be important, but data fails to show the variable significance.

different inner states were admissible. If a model considers more inner states than the number required for observability, the inner states in excess will be latent and the system will be unobservable.

- *The “muddiness” of the controlled system:* Another reason for unobservability results from insufficient knowledge regarding the relative importance of the inner states and regarding the interrelations between the inner states, as represented in Figure 3.15.

3.2.2.2 Detectability

A slightly weaker notion than observability is detectability. A system is detectable if and only if all of its unobservable modes are stable. This means that although not all inner states are manifest (observable), the ones that are latent (unobservable) constitute subspaces not requiring stabilisation.

To understand what is meant by “subspaces not requiring stabilisation”, consider that for an unobservable system the output $y(t)$ has a non-zero time trajectory in sub(state)space (z_1, z_2) , as represented in Figure 3.16.

Figure 3.16: Asymptotically stable trajectory $y(t)$ (Based on <http://www.math24.net/basic-concepts-of-stability-theory.html>, accessed on April 2013).

Mathematically an unobservable system is detectable if, in spite of the system’s output trajectory $y(t)$ not being uniquely determined, and being different from the zero trajectory φ determined by the observable subspace only, it converges to the zero trajectory as t tends to infinity. This means that instead of y there could be an alternative converging trajectory y' , say; however, since $\varepsilon(t)$ converges to zero as t tends to infinity whichever the trajectory, the system output is ensured to end up in the zero trajectory and, therefore, is stable. A system in which the observable subspace trajectory φ determines the output trajectory y asymptotically is called *detectable* (Willems and Polderman, 1997, p. 187). If the unobservable subspace of a system isn’t stable, the system trajectory doesn’t converge to the (observable subspace) zero trajectory and the system’s output can not be estimated: the system is undetectable.

Reframing

For complex socio-economic systems it is quite difficult to obtain a model suited for the understanding of what are the meaning-based needs or the unarticulated needs of the market/ users/ customers. Often there is a web of interrelations between needs — similar to the situation described in Figure 3.15 for subspace P — which, associated with the lack of accurate (and noise filtering) market research instruments leads to multiple possible interpretations of the market output data that is being gathered, and a difficulty in distinguishing the needs that are important to the market/ users/ customers.

When studying complex socio-economic systems there is little hope of finding an observable system. Luckily, in section 3.2.2.2 it was concluded that system observability (complete knowledge about the market's meaning-based needs) wasn't a necessary condition to enable the modelling of a controlled system. A control system can be unobservable but, if detectable, its output converges asymptotically to the observable subspace output. This means that if the market is detectable, unknown meaning-based needs have a small impact in the markets behaviour; the known meaning-based needs are those that really matter and these can be modelled from the knowledge of the market's behaviour (output) given some inputs.

There are therefore reasons to trust social sciences research, and, market research.

3.2.3 Controllability

Controllability is a dual to observability. In section 3.2.2 it was stated that for a system to be observable it was necessary that all inner states influenced the output; for a system to be controllable, all the inner states must be influenced by the input.

As discussed for observability, controllability is not always needed to “steer” a system in a certain trajectory. A concept dual to detectability can be defined — that of stabilizable systems — whenever it is possible to asymptotically steer a system to a desired trajectory.

It is also possible to distinguish different controllability subspaces of a controlled system. Figure 3.17 complements Figure 3.15 and includes the connections between system input and the different inner state subspaces.

Figure 3.17: Controllable, uncontrollable; observable, unobservable subspaces of a system relating input and output signals (based on Willems and Polderman, 1997, p. 190).

From Figure 3.17 it can be concluded that the subspaces P and Q are controllable. Subspaces P and R are the unobservable part of the statespace (as mentioned in section 3.2.2), therefore, although the input x acts upon subspace P , (for the system's output y chosen) it is impossible to observe the result of the input on that subspace. Another choice of output, different monitoring instruments would be needed to “reach” the latent states associated with subspace P .

On the other hand, Figure 3.17 (and also Figure 3.15) didn't represent the influence of ever present disturbances shown, for example, in Figure 3.12. Disturbances too influence the system output. And disturbances may influence the system subspaces in a way that is distinct from that of the manipulative input x represented in Figure 3.17.

For the understanding of a system's output and for a better modelling of a system's observer, monitoring of disturbances is important. Unfortunately this isn't always possible, due to the unawareness of the importance of certain disturbances, due to lack of resources to monitor a high number of inputs or due to the fact that some disturbances remain unmeasurable (because the measuring instruments need to be developed or simply because their existence still needs to be discovered).

Figure 3.17 shows that the reasons for uncontrollability are similar to those that justified unobservability, namely; selecting inputs which leave inner states (which could otherwise be manifest) uninfluenced, the possible dismissal of important inner states as irrelevant during the modelling of the controlled system, the existence of “uncharted” latent states.

Reframing

According to 3.2.2 the design thinking process of ethnographic research (that studies the relations between the controlled system's output and its inner states) can be related to the first-order cybernetic concept of observability. Since observability has a dual in controllability (a property that conveys information about the relations between system's input and its inner states), the design thinking process of rapid prototyping must be associated with controllability. An order-reversing duality could be formulated in the following way: Ethnographic market research lays downstream of the controlled system, researching its outputs; rapid prototyping lays upstream of the controlled system stimulating it with inputs.

The rapid prototyping process was presented in section 1.3.2 and described as a process that aimed at finding solutions by failing fast. Experiments ought to be simple and quick (Fogg, 2009).

In fact, for complex socio-economic systems this is probably the best strategy to filter false-positive creative concepts (and possibly, to identify the false-negative ones).

System Identification Theory uses this process for identifying system's transfer functions. A system's output is recorded for the widest possible spectrum of input frequencies, in order to have a "panoramic" overview of the system's behaviour. Nature too uses this process of solution finding engraved in the core of living organisms — the process of gene mutation. Heylighen and Joslyn (2001) gives an example:

"Let us illustrate this by considering a primitive aquatic organism whose control structure is a slightly more sophisticated version of the thermostat. To survive, this organism must remain in the right temperature zone, by moving up to warmer water layers or down to colder ones when needed. Its perception is a single temperature variable with 3 states $X = \textit{too hot}, \textit{too cold}, \textit{just right}$. Its variety of action consists of the 3 states $Y = \textit{go up}, \textit{go down}, \textit{do nothing}$. The organism's control knowledge consists of a set of perception-action pairs, or a function $f : X \rightarrow Y$. There are $3^3 = 27$ possible such functions, but the only optimal one consists of the rules $\textit{too hot} \rightarrow \textit{go down}$, $\textit{too cold} \rightarrow \textit{go up}$, and $\textit{just right} \rightarrow \textit{do nothing}$. The last rule could possibly be replaced by

either *just right* \rightarrow *go up* or *just right* \rightarrow *go down*. This would result in a little more expenditure of energy, but in combination with the previous rules would still keep the organism in a negative feedback loop around the ideal temperature. All 24 other possible combinations of rules would disrupt this stabilizing feedback, resulting in a runaway behavior that will eventually kill the organism.” (Heylighen and Joslyn, 2001, p. 21)

According to Heylighen and Joslyn’s example genetic mutation is responsible for providing the living organism with the widest spectrum of possible control functions (in this case 27), natural selection is responsible for eliminating all 24 combinations with non-stabilising positive feedback. Heylighen and Joslyn add: “The three negative feedback combinations will initially all remain, but because of competition, the most energy efficient combination will eventually take over. Thus internal variation of the control rules, together with natural selection by the environment eventually results in a workable model.” (Heylighen and Joslyn, 2001, p. 21)

Translating these system’s identification and natural selection examples into the business context would imply that viable market control solutions can be discovered if the market is subjected to the widest possible spectrum of control inputs (e.g., widest imaginable variations in product specifications). An analysis of the market behaviour (repudiation–indifference–acceptance) for each control input would enable the identification of the viable (accepted) product specifications.

This is precisely what rapid prototyping aims at. Rapid prototyping is inexpensive testing of many possible solutions to verify controllability and to single out solutions for which the market “resonates”.

3.3 Conclusion

Section 3.2.3 described rapid prototyping as a brute force expensive process of discovering solutions. In fact, for system identification most of the tested frequency spectrum can stay outside the working range of the system being identified (some of the test frequencies can even destroy the system). For the primitive aquatic organism example, several mutant generations can be annihilated before equilibrium is reached.

A better way of finding viable market control solutions is to have a hint at the reasons that make the market behave as it does. This hint is gained from ethnographic market research and the identification of the market’s meaning-based needs which determine the market behaviour. The designer’s process of framing–reframing of problems (recall section 1.2.1) taking into consideration market constraints imposed by the meaning–based needs (among others) already ensures that many false–positive solutions get discarded without the expense associated with actually testing them¹⁵.

Figure 3.18 presents a cybernetic interpretation of the design thinking process, representing the market (controlled system), the ethnographic research, the designer’s process of framing–reframing based on constraints imposed by the market’s meaning–based need (among others), and the rapid prototyping process of testing the designer’s potential market controlling solutions.

Figure 3.18: The design thinking process reframed: Interactions between ethnographic market research, the designer’s process of framing–reframing using market (among others) constraints, rapid prototyping, and the market.

From Figure 3.18 Design Thinking can be interpreted as a process that delivers innovative products/services and considers the following stages:

- Immersion into the market, using ethnographic research.

¹⁵To reduce the danger of eliminating false negatives, systematic tests with rejected solutions should be implemented.

- Framing/ reframing, to discover core problems and generate creative solutions.
- Rapid prototyping, to test the creative solutions and identify the innovative ones.

Part II
Design Thinking with a
focus on a single client:
Case study

Chapter 4

Design Thinking and eco-efficient innovative engineering

In this chapter two eco-efficient innovative engineering projects are presented and discussed. The first one is the development of a geothermal Heating, Ventilation and Air-Conditioning (HVAC) system for the head office building of a municipal enterprise. The second one is the development of a Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) heat production system for an industrial cheese making enterprise.

Sections 4.1 and 4.2 below describe the Clients, the Engineering Company that provided the eco-efficient engineering projects, and the relevant timelines of events. From the timelines of events it is possible to trace the path from creative eco-efficient solutions to innovative eco-efficient ones¹⁶.

Section 4.3 frames the two innovative eco-efficient projects according to the Design Thinking process and discusses the differences between Design Thinking for the development of innovative products/services for the market and Design Thinking for the development of innovative products/services for a single client.

4.1 Project A: Geothermal HVAC system

The Client: Small-sized municipal enterprise responsible for managing a municipal science and technological park. Dedicated to the development of partnerships between the municipality and technological enterprises in the renewable

¹⁶Section 3.2.1.1 discusses the difference between creativity and innovation. Innovation requires the acceptance of the product/ service by the market or by the single client.

energy sector, the Client adopted the following strategy: (i) develop a certified laboratory for testing photovoltaic solar panels, (ii) develop a Research and Development (R&D) team dedicated to the study of renewable energies.

To put this strategy into practice a new office building/ laboratory was needed. Due to the Client's values, the building should be net zero carbon emissions (carbon neutral). To achieve this goal the Client knew an innovative HVAC system was needed.

The Client had partnerships with several Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and used these partnerships to obtain consultancy.

The Engineering Company: Micro-sized enterprise dedicated to the design of eco-efficient engineering projects for buildings and industrial processes.

Timeline of events:

1. Procurement begins. Architects office is selected. HVAC system design is kept apart from architectural and all other engineering design specialities (e.g., plumbing, electricity, telecommunications). At the project inception the Client envisioned the use of a geothermal heat-pump HVAC system.
2. A HEI is contacted to supply consultancy regarding the design of a carbon neutral HVAC system. HEI consultant recommends the Engineering Company to the Client.
3. A first meeting between the Engineering Company and the Client takes place with the presence of the HEI consultant. The Engineering Company recognises the potential for using one of its independently developed (but yet to be tested) innovative HVAC systems and states so without giving details.
4. The Engineering Company contacts the HEI consultant and asks to arrange a meeting with the Client to present its innovative HVAC system in detail.
5. This meeting is scheduled and takes place with the presence of the Engineering Company, the Client, the HEI consultant and a consultant for the architectural and civil engineering specialities. After some debate the following conclusions are drawn:
 - i. The Engineering Company concludes that the proposed innovative HVAC system is infeasible given architectural constraints; however, an adapted version of the proposed system could circumvent the constraints and remain carbon neutral.

- ii. The consultant for architectural and civil engineering specialities concludes the proposed HVAC system is infeasible due to architectural and technical reasons and both the proposed and adapted system versions would be unreasonably expensive (no detailed assessment made).
 - iii. The HEI consultant concludes that further studies are needed to assess the viability of the Engineering Company's adapted system version.
 - iv. Although the Client had already heard of the innovative concept being proposed (a similar HVAC system had been publicised at that time), given the "compelling" cost-related arguments, the decision was to reject the innovative HVAC system. The Client decided to order the Engineering Company the design of a conventional heat-pump HVAC system, aware that this decision would compromise the initial goal of having a carbon neutral building.
6. A conventional heat-pump HVAC system was designed and delivered for bidding by the Engineering Company.
 7. The building construction bid was delayed and during this period the Client gathered further information on a geothermal HVAC system similar to the one that had been proposed by the Engineering Company. This event determined the Client's decision to return to its original objective of having a carbon neutral HVAC system and a carbon neutral building.
 8. The Client contacted the Engineering Company and asked to recover and deliver a design for an innovative geothermal HVAC system. This was still possible given the initial decision of excluding the HVAC system bid from the building construction bid.
 9. An innovative geothermal HVAC system was designed and delivered by the Engineering Company.
 10. The innovative geothermal HVAC system was built.

4.2 Project B: CSP heat production system for an industrial cheese making process

The Client: Small-sized industrial cheesemaker enterprise that had recently revamped its industrial facilities. However, since the industrial process hadn't been revamped, steam production and steam pipeline network were in need of urgent repair and jeopardising cheese production, because:

- The steam boiler would certainly fail on its next security inspection; this would mean losing the permit needed to use the boiler and since cheese production relied on steam (for the rotating mixers), cheese production was in danger.
- Steam boiler inefficiency and leaks in the steam pipeline network were significantly increasing the production energy costs.

The Client relied on consultancy provided by the Architect that had revamped the cheesemaking facilities.

The Engineering Company: The same described in Project A.

Timeline of events:

1. The Client contacted the Architect and asked for help with the steam network problem.
2. The Architect recommended the Engineering Company services.
3. The Engineering Company and the Architect visited to the cheesemaker industrial facilities.
4. The Engineering Company confirmed that the steam boiler had to be replaced and confirmed that extensive repairs were needed in the steam pipeline network. The Engineering Company also realized the potential for revamping the industrial heat production process, making use of renewable energy in an innovative and eco-efficient way.
5. After listening to the Architect's opinion, the Client agreed on the benefits of ordering an engineering study to analyse the viability of an innovative CSP heat production system.
6. The Engineering Company drafted a preliminary design for the CSP heat production system. Implementation of the draft design was divided into stages and the potentially critical issues (those that could hinder cheese production) were identified: (i) the feasibility of using thermal oil to exchange the necessary amount of heat; and, (ii) knowing if the switch from using steam to thermal oil would leave the final product (the cheese properties) unaffected.
7. The Engineering Company concluded that issue (i) was in fact not critical. To address issue (ii) it was concluded that a test had to be made before both the Engineering Company and the Client took any further action.

8. The Client's supplier of rotary mixers was contacted and the Engineering Company visited this supplier to discuss the manufacturing of a rotary mixer that used thermal oil instead of steam. It was agreed that if a prototype was built and if this prototype proved successful, the Client would buy/adapt several rotary mixers using thermal oil.
9. Thermal engineering instructions for the development of a prototype were discussed and delivered by the Engineering Company. An existing rotary mixer was used as the basis for the prototype and preliminary experiments proved that using thermal oil to exchange heat wouldn't hinder the cheese properties. However, due to thermophysical differences between thermal oil and steam, some structural adaptations had to be made to the typical rotary mixer design. These adaptations were left to the Supplier's engineering department.
10. The Supplier's delay in developing the structural adaptations and in presenting a functional rotary mixer forced the Client to reject the innovative solution.

4.3 Using the design thinking process to frame the projects

With some adaptations to the design thinking process presented in section 3.3, for the development of products/ services for markets, Table 4.1 associates projects A and B events with the design thinking process.

Immersion into the market stage was replaced by immersion into the Client's culture to fit the single client focus. Framing/ reframing was explicitly represented for both the Engineering Company and the Client.

From Table 4.1 it is possible to assess the fit and highlight specific characteristics of the design thinking process when it is applied to a single client:

- i. Immersion into the market — now, the Client's culture —, and ethnographic research remain valid. However, for the projects presented, ethnographic research was indirect; "hanging out" with the Client's consultants was the method used to gather information on the Client's past and culture. The difficulty in immersing into the Client's culture can be attributed to the gap (technological and cultural) separating designer and client. Finding ways to close this gap is essential for successful implementation of any innovative project.
- ii. Framing-reframing also remains valid. However, due to the proximity between product/service provider and client, the Client's reframing should follow

Table 4.1: Associating projects A and B events with stages of the design thinking process.

Stage\Project	A	B
Immersion into the Client's culture	Meetings with the Client. "Hanging out" with the HEI consultant	Meetings with the Client. "Hanging out" with the Architect
Engineering Company framing/reframing	Reframing from an initial geothermal HVAC system to an adapted version	Reframing from a conventional steam network system to a CSP heat production system
Client framing/ reframing	Reframing from conventional heat-pump HVAC system to innovative geothermal HVAC system	In spite of incomplete, some reframing from the conventional steam network system to the CSP heat production system was accomplished
Rapid prototyping	No rapid prototyping was made. The Client accepted the associated risk due to HEI consultant support to the project, favourable results presented in the literature for similar designs and the corporate embedded willingness to innovate	Prototyping of the issue that was critical to the process of cheese production was made to assess the innovative design viability

closely the reframing done by the Engineering Company. The Client has to undergo a process of unfreeze (a meaning to the Client's latent/tacit understanding of the problem must be made manifest), move (arguments for reframing the problem must be given and discussed), freeze (the Client must agree to reframe the problem in such a way that, for him — not only for the designer —, the innovative solution also makes sense; Engineering Company and Client must be united by a *shared belief*).

- iii. Rapid prototyping too remains valid when applying the design thinking process to a single client.

Conclusions

Converting mysteries to heuristics

A literature review on Design Thinking unveiled contradictory opinions about the usefulness of Design Thinking for the promotion of innovation. In spite of the reported success cases and the contributions of those that associate the design thinking process with a precise set of stages and tools — see chapter 2 —, it is argued that Design Thinking has a low success rate; some believe this happens because Design Thinking is more of an art than a science. Labelling Design Thinking as an art is, according to western cultural canons, a violent critique. We believe this critique is unfair.

Design Thinking should not be questioned because of its low success rate in delivering innovation, reframing Design Thinking using the cybernetic perspective — see chapter 3 — showed that given the complexity of the market and the multiple factors influencing it, failure to guarantee successful innovation ought not to be a surprise. The question that Design Thinking contenders should ask is — Is Design Thinking less successful than alternative methods? Namely, R&D performed by research institutions (in controlled environment) followed by R&D results commercialisation.

A characteristic (for many, a problem) of Design Thinking is that it contradicts the predominant descriptive science paradigm of first describing the system in minute detail, understand how the system behaves — under controlled conditions —, find solutions to specific problems and only then find out how the solutions that are valid for a controlled environment apply to the real world, subject to uncontrolled conditions. Design Thinking doesn't follow this (R&D) paradigm. But the “lens” of cybernetics showed that the design thinking process of immersion into the market/ client's culture, framing/ reframing, rapid prototyping made “organic” sense, and was similar to the process that living organisms used to survive and prosper.

Living organisms are naturally immersed in a natural environment. They are not in a controlled environment experiment like traditional descriptive science (and R&D) mandates. Living organisms are naturally creative: gene mutation

can be regarded as a form of embedded creativity. Living organisms immersed in a natural environment test their embedded creativity — their mutations — and, in this way, successful innovation is identified.

Design Thinking lack of “allegiance” to the predominant paradigm of descriptive science is probably the fundamental reason behind the unease Helen Walters’s (2011) sensed in “analysis–influenced C–suite members” — “relying on intuition and experience rather than on the ‘facts’ provided by spreadsheets and data, is anathema to most analysis–influenced C–suite members”. But this lack of allegiance can be seen as a strength and the better way to “convert *mysteries* to *heuristics*” in a time when “converting *heuristics* to *algorithms*” creates less and less value, as Roger Martin (2004) argued¹⁷.

The meaning of Design Thinking

We believe Design Thinking is the process that considers the following stages:

- Immersion into the market/ *Client’s culture*.
- Framing/ reframing of designers team *and* market/ client.
- Rapid prototyping.

This is an expansion of the definition given in section 3.3 (for markets) taking into consideration the study of projects A and B presented in chapter 4, for single clients.

An important difference between this process and that of section 3.3 is the inclusion of the market in the framing/ reframing stage. The literature refers only to the designers team framing/ reframing, but from the analysis of projects A and B in chapter 4 it became evident that the Client’s reframing should closely follow that of the designers team. When developing innovative products/ services for markets the same principle should apply. The market framing/ reframing is achieved through the use of marketing that also unfreezes, moves and freezes the customers or users into a mindset favourable to innovation. The importance of market framing/ reframing is on our opinion insufficiently emphasised in the Design Thinking literature.

Developing eco–efficient innovative engineering

The study of projects A and B presented in chapter 4 suggests that the design thinking process can help identify factors that determine successful eco–efficient innovative engineering projects.

¹⁷The highly codified and ambiguous language found in the literature to convey key Design Thinking concepts could contribute to associate Design Thinking and some form of art.

By framing eco-efficient innovative projects according to the design thinking process it can be concluded that:

- i. Immersion into the client’s culture is fundamental. This can be achieved in many ways. Whenever the gap between the client and the engineering company is significant, one possibility is relying on an agent or mediator that is familiar with the client’s culture and in whom the client trusts. Building trust will be one of the implicit objectives of all stages of the design thinking process.
- ii. Framing/ reframing to discover the core problem and a solution is a process that should be shared both by the engineering company and the client. The engineering company should lead the process but must be capable of changing the client’s mindset so that the solution makes sense for him too. To promote the client reframing the engineering company must realize that implementing an eco-efficient innovative project will be a learning experience for the client. Adequate information should be given to move the client from his initial conception to a shared belief compatible with the innovative solution. As mentioned previously, the design thinking process contributes to building client’s trust; since building trust takes time, the engineering company must be resilient during the framing/ reframing stage. For example, in the description of project A, section 4.1, the Client’s continued interest in gathering information about innovative geothermal HVAC systems (after the meeting that decided for the rejection of such a system) was decisive. The Client’s motivation to understand and learn led him back to his initial belief that a carbon neutral building was feasible, and to the recovery and completion of the innovative geothermal HVAC system.
- iii. Rapid prototyping is essential for innovative engineering projects. When dealing with single clients it becomes obvious that rapid prototyping is more than a way to test creative solutions; it is an ethical obligation, since unsuccessful solutions could seriously compromise the client’s activity. If a client does not wish to test an innovative engineering solution — as was the case for project A, section 4.1 — he should be well aware of the risks. Once again, rapid prototyping contributes for the engineering company and the client’s trust on the innovative solution.

Limitations and future research

The conclusions regarding the use of the design thinking process to frame eco-efficient engineering projects were based on the study of just two projects. This

represents a limitation and further research should study more projects to confirm the applicability and interest of Design Thinking.

Suggested topics for further research are:

- The comparison of Design Thinking success rate (in delivering innovation) and alternative innovation promotion methods, namely, R&D followed by commercialisation.
- Address the issue of the epistemological positioning associated with Design Thinking.

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